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Synthesis of bis[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-b:1',5'-d][1,2,4]triazine, a novel polynitrogenated heterocyclic system

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Abstract

2-Aryl [1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-d][1,2,4]triazine-5(6H)-thiones were methylated using methyl iodide in the presence of NaOH to give the corresponding 5-methylthio derivatives. Upon treatment with hydrazine hydrate, the latter were transformed to the corresponding 5-hydrazino derivatives via nucleophilic displacement. The 5-hydrazino compounds were reacted with orthoesters to furnish a novel heterocyclic system, bis[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-b:1',5'-d][1,2,4]triazines.

Keywords

Bis-triazolotriazine, Cyclizations, Heterocycles, Orthoester, Triazolotriazine